

Joining of C_f/SiC composites with Niobium alloy

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SUMMARY

A new surface modification to improve the weldability of C_f/SiC during brazing, and the gradient structures are designed to reduce the residual stress due to thermal mismatch between C_f/SiC and Nb-alloy. C_f/SiC is successfully brazed to Nb along with using TiCuZrNi as brazing filler metal, and the shear strength is as high as 124MPa.

Keywords: joining; modification; brazing; C_f/SiC; TiCuZrNi

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced silicon carbide matrix (C_f/SiC) composites have high intensity and excellent performance at high temperatures [1]. It has broad application in aerospace and energy etc. In engineering, C_f/SiC composite should be joined with metal [2]. As a result, the reliable joint of composite and metal is a key point to broaden the application of C_f/SiC composite.

The main methods to join C_f/SiC composite with metal are mechanical joining and brazing. Mechanical joining, with a complex joint, provides low airtightness and increases the weight and the size of components. The thermal stress of bolt joining is great, which hurts C_f/SiC composite greatly. Considering the high using temperature and reliability, brazing is more reasonable [3]. Brazing includes fusion welding, diffusion welding and braze welding. Because of the high melting point of C_f/SiC composite, fusion welding is not logical. The great pressure in diffusion welding can it is not adopted. Meanwhile, braze welding is promising choice for the joining of C_f/SiC composite with metal. To join the C_f/SiC composite with Nb alloy, three problems should be resolved. The first is the wet ability of solder to C_f/SiC composite. The second is the great thermal stress induced by the great difference of thermal expansion coefficient between C_f/SiC composite and Nb alloy. The third is the good mechanical property of solder at high temperatures. Therefore, surface modification of C_f/SiC composite is necessary for the ideal joining face. Zr, with high chemical activity [4], has better affinity with C and Si. The thermal expansion coefficient of Zr compounds are between that of C_f/SiC composite and Nb alloy. Consequently, Zr is selected as metalized element for surface modification, and TiCuZrNi amorphous foil is used as solder to realize the reliable joint between C_f/SiC composite and Nb alloy.

In the present study, Zr metalized coating was fabricated on the surface of C_f/SiC composite. Then, the metalized composite was joined with Nb alloy by TiCuZrNi amorphous foil. The morphologies and phase composition of metalized coating and interlayer were characterized and the formation and mechanical property of the joint were studied.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The C_f/SiC composites used in this work were made with precursor infiltration and pyrolysis (PIP) method in the National University of Defense Technology in China. The samples were $15 \times 10 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$ in size. The used Nb alloy was NbHf10-M, with $20 \times 5 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ in size. The solder was TiCuZrNi amorphous foil, with the thickness of 0.06 mm.

Equal mole of NaCl-KCl and some K_2ZrF_6 were mixed together as molten salt. The C_f/SiC composite and Zr powder were put into the mixed salt. All the compositions were embedded into alumina crucible. The assembly was heated to $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and kept for 3 h in Ar atmosphere. After furnace cooling to room temperature, the composite samples were taken out from the assembly and cleaned to get rid of the salt.

The joint is of “sandwich” structure (as Fig.1 shows). The face vertical to carbon fibres is choose as joining face to join with Nb alloy and the joining area is $15 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$. The parameters of brazing are at $930 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min in vacuum and furnace cooling. Some press is necessary in the brazing process.

Fig.1 Structure of assembled sample of C_f/SiC and Nb alloy

Thermal shock tests were carried out in furnace at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in atmosphere. The samples were put into the furnace. After kept for 5 min, the samples were carried out quickly and cooled to room temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phase composition and morphologies of Zr metallized coating

Fig.2 is the X-ray patterns of Zr metallized coating on the surface of C_f/SiC composite. The main phase compositions of the coating are Zr, Zr_3O , ZrC and Zr_2Si . The coating can enhance the surface energy of C_f/SiC composite and improve the wetting of liquid solder to C_f/SiC composite. Zr, Zr_3O , ZrC and Zr_2Si are compounds with metallic bond, which increase the bond strength of metallized coating C_f/SiC composite [5]. The thermal expansion coefficient of the metallized coating is between that of C_f/SiC composite and Nb alloy [6]. The residual stress between the composite and Nb alloy during brazing process are reduced by the coating.

As Fig.3 shows, the coating binds tightly with the C_f/SiC composite and diffused into the inner pores of the composite to seal them. The solder can wet the Zr metallized coating well. After brazing process, the solder diffusing into the pores of composite form “nails” and increase the valid joint areas to improve the joining strength.

Fig.2 X-ray diffraction patterns of the zirconium metallized coating on the C_f/SiC composites

Fig.3 The morphology of the cross-sectional feature of C_f/SiC composites

The morphologies of the joint

Fig.4 (a) and (b) are the morphologies of joint of Zr metallized C_f/SiC composite and Nb alloy. The joining material binds tightly with C_f/SiC composite and Nb alloy. During brazing process, the molten solder diffuse into the pores of composite and the joining area is increased. As a result, the joining intensity can be also increased. The joining materials have three layers. The inner layer is very thin and characterized as black (A in Fig.4 (b)). The medium layer includes B phase and C phase with different color in Fig.4 (b). The outer layer is close to Nb alloy (D in Fig.4 (b)). EDS patterns show that A includes Ti, Si and Zr elements. B and C phase include Ti, Cu, Zr and Ni. The atom ratio of Cu and Ti is close to 1:2 and that of Ni and Zr is nearly 1:1. The atom ratio of Ti, Cu, Zr and Ni is close to the initial composition of the solder. D phase includes Ti, Cu, Zr, Ni and Nb. It could be concluded that the medium layer including B and C phases are formed by the frozen of molten solder, and the outer layer is formed by the diffusion of Ti in molten solder and Nb in alloy, which could bind the alloy with the solder tightly. Ti elements diffuse into the C_f/SiC composite and react with it to form inner layer, which binds the solder tightly with the composite.

Fig.4 The morphology of the joint interface

Fig.5 Elements linear scanning of the joint interface

Table 1 Results of energy spectrum analysis (mol %)

Position	Si	Ti	Zr	Cu	Ni	Nb
A	5.15	84.83	5.72	1.17	1	2.12
B	2.12	40.73	10.03	18.1	14.66	4.35
C	2.01	58.74	5.35	24.61	6.7	2.59
D	1.8	68.53	6.26	2.88	2.32	18.21

The joining intensity

After the same brazing process, the joint of uncoated composite with Nb alloy was broken, while the metallized composite joined tightly with Nb alloy. The shearing strength of the joint between metallized composite and Nb alloy was 124 MPa. After thermal shocks for 5 times, the residual shearing strength was still 70 MPa.

Fig.6 is the fracture surface of the joint between metallized composite and Nb alloy. The fracture surface is covered by the cracked fibres and matrix SiC. The fracture surface is smooth. Area A is the matrix SiC and fibres pulled out from that. Some white area (characterized as B) is the cracked solder. The cracks generate at the interfaces between fibres and matrix, and extend through the interfaces. Carbon fibres should be pulled out firstly, then crack. Before cracking, a lot of fibres resist shearing stress and protect the joint. When the shearing stress is big enough, the cracks will generate. With the increasing of shearing stress, the cracks extend. The debonding and pulling out of fibres can enhance the property of the joint.

Conclusions

- (1) The Zr metallized coating bond tightly with C_f/SiC composite and the main phase compositions of coating are Zr, Zr₃O, ZrC and Zr₂Si.
- (2) During brazing process, the solder diffuses into Nb alloy and a transition layer formed near the interlayer, which binds the solder tightly with Nb alloy. Ti elements of the solder diffuse into the C_f/SiC composite and react with it, which bind the solder tightly with the C_f/SiC composite. The solder diffuses into the pores of composite and forms “nails” to enhance the intensity of joint.
- (3) In shearing test, the C_f/SiC composite of the joined sample crack firstly. The shearing intensity of the joint is 124 MPa.

Fig.6 The fracture surface of the joint

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